

**TRNSYS Type107
Part load simulation of single staged absorption chillers
in quasi steady states**

**Contribution to a design tool
for solar assisted air conditioning systems
developed in IEA TASK25 Subtask B**

Final report

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1 Introduction

Within the research project of the International Energy Agency (IEA) „Solar assisted air conditioning of buildings” (TASK25) a design tool is developed to enable a pre-design of solar cooling projects even in an early planning phase.

By means of an annual simulation algorithm with a time step of approximately one hour, different solar assisted cooling systems (SAC-Systems) can be compared taking part load conditions as quasi steady states under consideration.

The following possible cold generation facilities are intended to be supplied by solar heat:

- Desiccant and evaporative cooling systems,
- Absorption chillers,
- Adsorption chillers.

For the simulation of the chillers, calculation methods for the part load behaviour are necessary, whose accuracy - related to manufacturers data - is sufficient enough and whose input data are free available. A separate measurement of performance data in addition to manufacturers data should be avoided.

The following report is a contribution to the simulation model of absorption chillers, which can be used in the design tool for solar assisted air-conditioning systems developed in the IEA TASK25 research project.

For now the model is validated to a single staged absorption chiller with H₂O/LiBr as working fluid. Nevertheless it may be used with manufacturers data of NH₃/H₂O chillers or any other working pair as long as the linearity requirements are met. The computer code is written in FORTRAN77 using the syntax of TRNSYS 15. The author would like to thank for the financial support of the Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology (BMW_i).

2 General description

In the next chapters the development of a computer code (the so called TRNSYS Type107) is described, which simulates single staged H₂O/LiBr-absorption chillers. The theory is based on the method of characteristic equations for the "delta-delta-T-function" ($\Delta\Delta t$) developed by F. Ziegler et.al. (mode=1). This method has been enlarged for a special chiller (the Yazaki WFC10) with a non linear characteristic (mode=2). In contrary to the first case the second one is not universal (see [1] and Mathematical Description for more information).

A necessary requirement for utilization of the characteristic equation method is, that the following assumptions of linearity are fulfilled for the absorption chiller, which has to be simulated.

- All enthalpy coefficients are constant.
- All heat transfer coefficients $Y_x=A_x \cdot k_x$ are constant.
- The unavoidable heat losses $Q_{G,loss}$ und $Q_{A,loss}$ are constant, which means they are independent of $\Delta\Delta t$.

As an example and for validation manufactures data for absorption chillers of YORK INTERNATIONAL, SERIES YIA and YAZAKI WFC10 are used.

Within the research work about different absorption chillers it has been found, that for the Yazaki WFC10 chiller the assumptions of linearity are inappropriate over a wide range of operation conditions. Therefore a special mode is included which takes the specific part load behaviour of the WFC10 into account.

3 Mathematical description

3.1 MODE 1

The internal temperatures of the four heat exchangers (Generator, Absorber, Condenser, Evaporator) can be combined by using Dühring's rule for the dissolution field of aqueous lithium bromide.

$$(T_G - T_A) = (T_C - T_E) \cdot B \quad (1)$$

Assuming equal heat fluxes inside and outside the absorption chiller (adiabatic heat exchangers) the internal temperatures T_x can be expressed as a function of the external temperatures t_x .

$$T_G = t_G - Q_E G/Y_G - Q_{G,loss}/Y_G \quad (2.1)$$

$$T_E = t_E - Q_E E/Y_E \quad (2.2)$$

$$T_A = t_A - Q_E A/Y_A - Q_{A,loss}/Y_A \quad (2.3)$$

$$T_C = t_C - Q_E K/Y_C \quad (2.4)$$

The coefficients G, A and C in equation (2.x) standing for the internal specific enthalpy differences at the corresponding heat exchangers related to the specific enthalpy differences at the evaporator. Y_x are the heat transfer coefficients $Y_x = A_x \cdot k_x$.

By substituting the equations (2) into (1) eliminates the internal temperatures.

$$[t_C - t_E + Q_E (K/Y_C - 1/Y_E)] B = [t_G - t_A - Q_E (G/Y_G + A/Y_A) - Q_{G,loss}/Y_G - Q_{A,loss}/Y_A] \quad (3)$$

Using the equation of definition for the characteristic temperature difference ($\Delta\Delta t$ -function)

$$\Delta\Delta t := (t_G - t_A) - (t_C - t_E) \cdot B \quad (4)$$

and rearranging the enthalpy and heat transfer coefficients into s_E and $\Delta\Delta t_{min_E}$, leads to the characteristic equation for the cooling capacity.

$$Q_E = s_E \cdot \Delta\Delta t - s_E \cdot \Delta\Delta t_{min_E} \quad (5)$$

If the gradient (s_E) and axis interval ($s_E \cdot \Delta\Delta t_{min_E}$) are constant, the part load of an absorption chiller can be expressed as a linear function of $\Delta\Delta t$. F. Ziegler et al. have shown that under steady state conditions and constant solution flow rates the assumption of constant parameters is permitted at most times.

The derivation of the characteristic equation can also be applied to the generator heat flux. Thereby the internal enthalpy differences have to be correlated to the specific enthalpy difference in the generator, which is used to evaporate the cooling agent (H_2O). The remaining ration (for heating the weak solution) is considered in $Q_{G,loss}$ and $\Delta\Delta t_{min_G}$ respectively.

By means the characteristic equation for the generator heat flux is derived with different slope and axis interval.

$$Q_G = s_G \cdot \Delta\Delta t - s_G \cdot \Delta\Delta t_{\min G} \quad (6)$$

The same procedure is done for the combined heat flux of absorber and condenser, whereas a serial flow form absorber to condenser with constant mass flow rate is assumed. This combination takes into account that the absorber outlet temperature is commonly not specified in manufacturers data. The characteristic equation for the extracted heat from absorber and condenser can be expressed as

$$Q_{AC} = s_{AC} \cdot \Delta\Delta t - s_{AC} \cdot \Delta\Delta t_{\min AC}. \quad (7)$$

By means of the absorber-condenser-combination the equation of definition for the $\Delta\Delta t$ -function is reduced to

$$\Delta\Delta t - t_G + (1+B) \cdot t_{AC} - B \cdot t_E = 0. \quad (8)$$

According to a former work of F. Ziegler one can use the arithmetic instead of the thermodynamic mean temperature for the heat flux calculation with only a small loss in accuracy [3] if the temperature difference is not to high. By means the external outlet temperatures of the heat exchangers can be calculated with

$$t_{x,o} = 2 \cdot t_x - t_{x,i} \quad (9)$$

Index x stands for the variable Index $_{AC, E, G}$ according to the heat exchanger. Index $_i$ and $_o$ is used for Input and Output respectively. By substituting equation (9) to the external energy balances leads to

$$Q_x = 2 \cdot m_x \cdot c_{px} \cdot (t_{x,i} - t_x). \quad (10)$$

For the energy fluxes the following polarity sign convention has to be mentioned:

An energy flux into the absorption machine is positive (generator, evaporator); an extracted energy flux from the chiller is negative (absorber, condenser). This has to be noticed when defining the Parameters (see TRNSYS Component Configuration and Example).

After equalising the external energy balances with the characteristic equations (5), (6), (7) and using the equation of definition for the $\Delta\Delta t$ -function (8) a four dimensional, linear equation system is found.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\Delta t - t_G - B t_E + (1+B) t_{AC} &= 0 & (11) \\ s_G \Delta\Delta t + 2 m_G c_{pG} t_G + 0 + 0 &= 2 m_G c_{pG} t_{G,i} + s_G \Delta\Delta t_{\min G} \\ s_E \Delta\Delta t + 0 + 2 m_E c_{pE} t_E + 0 &= 2 m_E c_{pE} t_{E,i} + s_E \Delta\Delta t_{\min E} \\ s_{AC} \Delta\Delta t + 0 + 0 + 2 m_{AC} c_{pAC} t_{AC} &= 2 m_{AC} c_{pAC} t_{AC,i} + s_{AC} \Delta\Delta t_{\min AC} \end{aligned}$$

By solving the linear equation system with the Gaussian elimination algorithm with maximum Pivoting the external mean temperatures (t_G , t_E , t_{AC}) and the $\Delta\Delta t$ -functional can be calculated. With utilization of equation (9) and (10) all outlet temperatures and heat capacities can be calculated.

To solve the equation system the values for slope (s_x) and axis interval ($\Delta\Delta t_{\min x}$) have to be known. These values can be determined from only two reference operation data under steady state conditions like they are published by manufacturers in the chiller's characteris-

tic. These characteristic parameters can be taken as constant for every part load condition as long as the linearity assumptions are matched (see [1]). Since the linearity assumptions require e.g. constant heat transfer coefficients which is not exactly true for real processes, it has been shown in [3] and [5] that the mismatch of simulated data to manufacturers data is reduced from 10% to 5%, when the characteristic parameters are not taken as constant but as linear functions of $\Delta t_{ACE} = t_{AC} - t_E$.

The characteristic equations for the three heat fluxes have to be rewritten as follows:

$$Q_E = s_E(\Delta t_{ACE}) \cdot \Delta \Delta t - s_E(\Delta t_{ACE}) \cdot \Delta \Delta t_{min_E}(\Delta t_{ACE}) \quad (12a)$$

$$Q_G = s_G(\Delta t_{ACE}) \cdot \Delta \Delta t - s_G(\Delta t_{ACE}) \cdot \Delta \Delta t_{min_G}(\Delta t_{ACE}) \quad (12a)$$

$$Q_{AC} = s_{AC}(\Delta t_{ACE}) \cdot \Delta \Delta t - s_{AC}(\Delta t_{ACE}) \cdot \Delta \Delta t_{min_{AC}}(\Delta t_{ACE}) \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{where: } s_X(\Delta t_{ACE}) = s_{XI} \cdot (\Delta t_{ACE}) + s_{XII} \quad (13a)$$

$$\Delta \Delta t_{min_X}(\Delta t_{ACE}) = r_{XI} \cdot (\Delta t_{ACE}) + r_{XII} \quad (13b)$$

Unfortunately the increase in accuracy leads to an increase of computation effort:

- To find the values (s_{XI} , s_{XII} , r_{XI} , r_{XII}) to determine the characteristic parameters (s_X and $\Delta \Delta t_{min_X}$), four reference operation points have to be evaluated from manufacturers data instead of two.
- The calculation of the characteristic parameters have to be done every simulation time step, because they depend on the actual operation temperatures t_{AC} and t_E .

During the 5th Expert meeting in Lisbon [5] it has been decided:

- 1) To use the improved calculation method, which is based on four operation states.
- 2) To employ the necessary values (s_{XI} , s_{XII} , r_{XI} , r_{XII}) for the characteristic equations in a database in order to avoid the analysis of the reference states during the (yearly) system simulation.

In conclusion for each absorption chiller 13 parameters are needed which are stored in a database. These values are derived from an external analysis of four reference operation states from manufacturers part load characteristics. The data analysis is not included in the TRNSYS Type. It has to be done only once to fill the database (see example).

Remark to specific isobaric heat of water (c_p in kJ/(kg*K)).

Although it is recommended to use the IAPWS97 methods [6] for calculation of the properties of water in technical aspects the following regressions (developed by ISE Freiburg) are used. By means the same property data are used in the models for ab- and adsorption chillers (TYPE107 and TYPE221). The difference to the IAPWS-values is lower then 0.1% in the interesting range between 0 and 100°C and 1 to 10 bar respectively.

3.2 MODE 2

The characteristic equations used in mode 1 are linear equations, only if the slope and the losses are independent of $\Delta\Delta t$, which means they are independent of the part load condition. If these assumptions of linearity are fulfilled for the considered absorption chiller the manufacturers data for part load conditions can be simulated with a deviation below 5% in mode 1.

Unfortunately the often used Yazaki WFC10 chiller does not match the assumptions of linearity. As it is seen from manufacturers data sheets the characteristics of the Yazaki chiller can be classified into three regions (Figure 1).

- In region B1 the cooling capacity scales with a linear function of $\Delta\Delta t$.
- In region B3 (where the cooling capacity is low) there are some non linear effects which also can be observed at "normal" absorption chillers with almost linear characteristics. They will not be considered here.
- Between region B1 and B2, within an interval not more than one or two Kelvin the expected further increase of the cooling capacity diminishes and the capacity is kept constant although $\Delta\Delta t$ is still growing.

Figure 1: Principle of characteristics for WFC10.

The additional parameter $\Delta\Delta t_{lim}$ characterises the relatively sharp bend points which are the border between region B1 and B2.

It has been found that $\Delta\Delta t_{lim}$ can be correlated with the inlet temperature difference of hot and cooling water ($\Delta t_{gaci} = t_{gi} - t_{aci}$) and the slope of the capacity characteristic depends mainly on the cooling water temperature itself (Figure 2 and 3).

Figure 2: $\Delta\Delta t_{lim\dot{Q}_e}$ as function of Δt_{gaci}

Figure 3: Slope $s_{\dot{Q}_e}$ as function of t_{aci}

This limiting temperature difference is variable in general. Unfortunately it is not possible to calculate the losses (expressed by the parameter $\Delta\Delta t_{min}$) in the same easy way. Up to now one has to use a second order multi regression equation.

$$\Delta\Delta t_{min} = a \cdot t_{aci}^2 + b \cdot t_{aci} + c \cdot t_{gi} \cdot t_{aci}^2 + d \cdot t_{gi}^2 \cdot t_{aci}^2 + e \cdot t_{gi} \cdot t_{aci} + f \cdot t_{gi}^2 \cdot t_{aci} + g \cdot t_{gi} + h \cdot t_{gi}^2 + i \quad (13)$$

In order to increase the accuracy of the model this regression function is used for all characteristic parameters (sharp bend point $\Delta\Delta t_{lim}$, slope s and $\Delta\Delta t_{min}$). The regression values are shown in table 1. More information about the model configuration is shown in [4].

X	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
$\Delta\Delta t_{lim\dot{Q}_e}$	3,01E+00	-1,51E+02	-6,89E-02	3,94E-04	3,41E+00	-1,94E-02	-4,18E+01	2,41E-01	1,89E+03
$s_{\dot{Q}_e}$	-8,13E-02	4,70E+00	1,47E-03	-6,41E-06	-8,33E-02	3,70E-04	1,17E+00	-5,26E-03	-6,39E+01
$\Delta\Delta t_{min\dot{Q}_e}$	-5,77E+00	3,08E+02	1,24E-01	-6,60E-04	-6,54E+00	3,43E-02	8,56E+01	-4,44E-01	-4,09E+03
$\Delta\Delta t_{limCOP}$	8,69E+00	-4,63E+02	-2,04E-01	1,19E-03	1,08E+01	-6,32E-02	-1,42E+02	8,35E-01	6,10E+03
s_{COP}	1,98E-03	-1,19E-01	-2,50E-05	2,22E-07	1,64E-03	-1,37E-05	-2,73E-02	2,15E-04	1,89E+00
$\Delta\Delta t_{minCOP}$	-8,27E+00	4,32E+02	1,85E-01	-1,06E-03	-9,60E+00	5,48E-02	1,23E+02	-7,05E-01	-5,57E+03

Table 1: Regression values for the modified characteristic equations of COP and cooling capacity for WFC10

The part load characteristics of the WFC10 can now be determined by using the modified characteristic equations

$$\dot{Q}_e = s_{\dot{Q}_e}(t_{gi}, t_{aci}) \cdot (\Delta\Delta t^{**} - \Delta\Delta t_{min\dot{Q}_e}(t_{gi}, t_{aci})) \quad (14a)$$

$$COP = s_{COP}(t_{gi}, t_{aci}) \cdot (\Delta\Delta t^{**} - \Delta\Delta t_{minCOP}(t_{gi}, t_{aci})) \quad (14b)$$

$$\text{where } \Delta\Delta t^{**} = \begin{cases} \Delta\Delta t^* & \text{when } \Delta\Delta t^* < \Delta\Delta t_{lim} \\ \Delta\Delta t_{lim} & \text{when } \Delta\Delta t^* \geq \Delta\Delta t_{lim} \end{cases}$$

with the known parameters for $\Delta\Delta t_{lim}$, s and $\Delta\Delta t_{min}$ in combination with the inlet temperatures for hot, cold and cooling water.

4 TRNSYS Component Configuration

4.1 MODE 1

To simulate an absorption chiller with MODE=1 the user has to specify 16 parameters (see below). These values represent the result of the manufacturer's data analysis which is carried out externally. For the design tool of TASK25 Subtask B the values are stored in a database (see example in chapter 5).

PARAMETER

1	Mode	calculation mode must set to 1 (user supplied data)	-
2	rgl	First parameter for axis interval (generator)	K/K
3	rgll	Second parameter for axis interval (generator)	K
4	sgl	First parameter for slope calculation (generator)	$\text{kJ}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{K})$
5	sgll	Second parameter for slope calculation (generator)	$\text{kJ}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{K}^2)$
6	rel	First parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	K/K
7	rell	Second parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	K
8	sel	First parameter for slope calculation (evaporator)	$\text{kJ}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{K})$
9	sell	Second parameter for slope calculation (evaporator)	$\text{kJ}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{K}^2)$
10	racl	First parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	K/K
11	racll	Second parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	K
12	saccl	First parameter for slope calculation (absorber and condenser)	$\text{kJ}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{K})$
13	sacll	Second parameter for slope calculation (absorber and condenser)	$\text{kJ}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{K}^2)$
14	B	Dühring parameter	-
15	tcw1	Minimum cooling water temperature for parameter 2 to 13	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
15	tcw2	Maximum cooling water temperature for parameter 2 to 13	$^{\circ}\text{C}$

INPUTS

1	tgi	External inlet temp. to generator	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
2	mgI	External mass flow rate to generator	kg/h
3	tei	External inlet temp. to evaporator	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
4	mei	External mass flow rate to evaporator	kg/h
5	taci	external inlet temp. to absorber (and condenser)	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
6	maci	external mass flow rate to absorber (and condenser)	kg/h

OUTPUTS

1	tgo	external outlet temp. to generator	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
2	mgo	external mass flow rate to generator	kg/h
3	teo	external outlet temp. to evaporator	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
4	meo	external mass flow rate to evaporator	kg/h
5	taco	external outlet temp. from (absorber and) condenser	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
6	maco	external mass flow rate from (absorber and) condenser	kg/h
7	Qg	Source heat to generator	kJ/h
8	Qe	Chilled water capacity	kJ/h
9	Qac	Cooling water capacity	kJ/h
10	COP	Coefficient of performance	-
11	ddT	ddT functional value	K

The last two parameters are used to reduce the possibility of extrapolation errors. The part load behaviour can only be simulated in time steps where the cooling water inlet temperature is inside the interval of t_{cw1} and t_{cw2} (these are the cooling water temperatures used in the data analysis). A tolerance of 5% ($\min(t_{cw1}; t_{cw2}) \cdot 0,95 < t_{ACi}(TIME) < \max(t_{cw1}; t_{cw2}) \cdot 1,05$) is allowed otherwise the simulation is stopped.

Although the range of chilled water temperatures is unrestricted in the model it has to be considered that the verification calculations have only been carried out for chilled water temperatures of 6°C only (restriction is caused by limited manufacturers data).

4.2 MODE 2

MODE 2 does not require any further value than the first parameter. The values of Table 1 (needed to determine the characteristic equations) are set in the source code because this model is restricted to simulate the Yazaki WFC10. The configuration for the inputs and outputs is the same as in mode 1.

PARAMETER

1	Mode	calculation mode must set to 2 (for WFC10)	-
INPUTS			
1	tgi	External inlet temp. to generator	°C
2	mgj	External mass flow rate to generator	kg/h
3	tei	External inlet temp. to evaporator	°C
4	mei	External mass flow rate to evaporator	kg/h
5	taci	external inlet temp. to absorber (and condenser)	°C
6	maci	external mass flow rate to absorber (and condenser)	kg/h
OUTPUTS			
1	tgo	external outlet temp. to generator	°C
2	mgo	external mass flow rate to generator	kg/h
3	teo	external outlet temp. to evaporator	°C
4	meo	external mass flow rate to evaporator	kg/h
5	taco	external outlet temp. from (absorber and) condenser	°C
6	maco	external mass flow rate from (absorber and) condenser	kg/h
7	Qg	Source heat to generator	kJ/h
8	Qe	Chilled water capacity	kJ/h
9	Qac	Cooling water capacity	kJ/h
10	COP	Coefficient of performance	-
11	ddT	ddT functional value	K

5 Verification and Example

The following parameters have been found from manufacturers data, YORK INTERNATIONAL Series YIA Type 1A1 with a nominal cooling capacity of 422 kW.

PAR	Description	
1	calculation mode must set to 1 (user supplied data / database)	1 -
2	First parameter for axis interval (generator)	6,33 K/K
3	Second parameter for axis interval (generator)	- 0,14 K
4	First parameter for slope calculation (generator)	48.357 kJ/(h·K)
5	Second parameter for slope calculation (generator)	- 24,93 kJ/(h·K ²)
6	First parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	4,53 K/K
7	Second parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	0,01 K
8	First parameter for slope calculation (evaporator)	34.522 kJ/(h·K)
9	Second parameter for slope calculation (evaporator)	27,31 kJ/(h·K ²)
10	First parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	5,54 K/K
11	Second parameter for axis interval (evaporator)	-0,08 K
12	First parameter for slope calculation (absorber and condenser)	- 82.879 kJ/(h·K)
13	Second parameter for slope calculation (absorber and condenser)	- 2,38 kJ/(h·K ²)
14	Dürring parameter	1,2 -
15	Minimum cooling water temperature for parameter 2 to 13	27 °C
15	Maximum cooling water temperature for parameter 2 to 13	41 °C

Table 2: Example values for determination of characteristic parameters.

The results of the TRNSYS simulation with TYPE 107, which have been carried out by using the parameters of table 2, are shown below. More information about the verification procedure is available in [3].

Figure 4 Cooling capacity versus $\Delta\Delta t$ -function simulated and manufacturers data for Series YIA Type 1A1.

Figure 5: Deviation of simulated and manufacturers data for COP of YIA Type 1A1 at cooling water temperatures of 27, 35 and 41°C.

In figure 6 the deviation of simulated and manufacturers data for COP and cooling capacity are shown for the Yazaki WFC10 chiller.

Figure 6: Deviation of simulated and manufacturers data for COP and cooling capacity of WFC10 at cooling water temperatures of 24, 29,5 and 31°C.

From figure 4 to 6 it is seen that the modified characteristic equations can be used to simulate the part load behaviour of H₂O/LiBr absorptions chillers over a wide load range with an error lower the 10% or 5% respectively. It is recommended to use the algorithm in the design tool of TASK 25 Subtask B. Further work has to be done to enlarge the database.

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